

D6.2 (M18) - First report on standards and best practices (an ELIXIR Norway ELIXIR₃ deliverable)

Project name: ELIXIR₃ - strengthening the Norwegian Node of ELIXIR
Project number: [322392](#)
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Date: 1. October 2023
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10843268
Keywords: Implementation of standards, molecular-based and biodiversity datasets, harmonisation of community standards, FAIRification of sampling data, EBP-Nor project, national resource.

Context

Background and info

ELIXIR₃ - strengthening the Norwegian Node of ELIXIR, has engaged in the implementation of standards and best practices in life science. This report, Deliverable 6.2, concerns the implementation efforts for biodiversity related standards by Work Package 6 (WP6). To effectively map, link and FAIRify molecular-based data to biodiversity information, there is a critical need to harmonise community standards within biodiversity communities. This involves the implementation of gold standards and best practices for biodiversity datasets linked to molecular biology data and files. Achieving this harmonisation necessitates close collaboration with Norwegian biodiversity infrastructures, networks and projects while ensuring alignment with relevant international efforts.

Challenges addressed

The key challenge is successfully implementing standards for molecular biology and includes the FAIRification of sampling efforts by encouraging the use of published standards through necessary training, guidance, and services. To achieve consistent and FAIR data in molecular biodiversity necessitates the integration of standards like Minimum Information about any (X) Sequence (MIxS), European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) checklists, and European Reference Genome Atlas (ERGA) for initiatives and projects in biodiversity using molecular data.

Objectives

Assist biodiversity projects, e.g. the EBP-Norway project¹, to implement and manage FAIR metadata through published standards in frameworks like attribute manifests, sampling sheets, and repositories for contextual and molecular data. This facilitates alignment to ENA requirements as well as the establishment of protocols and practices that encourage better sharing of biodiversity and molecular-based datasets, ultimately contributing to increased data reuse and repurposing.

¹The EBP-Norway project ([KSP: A Norwegian BioGenome initiative: the initial Launch phase, Project Number: 326819](#)) represents the first operational sequencing phase for eukaryotic species in the Norwegian node of the global [EBP project](#). This phase aims to sample, sequence and publish the first batch of 100 eukaryotic genomes to establish a modus operandi for future phases and upscaling of the project.

Delivery

- WP6 created an attribute manifest based on the ENA and ERGA standards, holding attribute descriptions and definitions for handling sample information in the EBP-Nor project. This involved:
 - The implementation and mapping of attributes from (1) the ENA data submission requirements for raw data reads and assemblies of eukaryotic genomes, (2) the ERGA manifest documents (<https://github.com/ERGA-consortium/ERGA-sample-manifest>), (3) and the ENA Darwin Tree of Life (DToL) checklist (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/ERC000053>).
 - The implemented attributes were aligned with the EBP-Nor project umbrella at ENA (Bioproject id: [PRJEB65317](#)). This ensured hierarchical linkage with the global EBP project ([PRJNA533106](#)) while following the DToL structure for attributes at all levels of the ENA submission protocol.
 - The implementation (attribute definitions) were expressed and configured in the EBP-Nor database system (<https://databases.ebpnor.org>), which is based on the Contextual Biodata Framework (CBF) (<https://gitlab.com/uit-sfb/cbf>). The complete attribute specifications are listed in each database table at the EBP-Nor database pages:
 - [Species definitions](#)
 - [Isolate definitions](#)
 - [Specimen definitions](#)
 - [Sequencing definitions](#)
 - [Assembly definitions](#)
 - The implementation ensures the consistency of datasets in the EBP-Nor database system by enforcing validation of attributes based on the

above-mentioned standards. Consistent data were guided using controlled vocabularies (CV), ontologies, accessions, numeric fields, date fields, and free text fields accordingly.

- The mentioned standards were additionally implemented in a sampling sheet for offline data collection, accessible from the main database page (<https://databases.ebpnor.org>).
- WP6 with T6.2 will continue to support, update, and extend the standards for EBP-Nor when needed during the lifetime of the ELIXIR₃ project and the EBP-Norway project.
- WP6 with T6.2 will provide support and offer assistance in implementing standards for upcoming projects using molecular data in biodiversity research.
- WP6 with T6.2 will take action and create, curate and update a national resource library for standards and best practices related to molecular biodiversity. The resource library and how-to practices is planned to be operated under the elixir.no/rdm-lookup/biodiversity pages and guided based on the input from the Biodiversity Working Group (WP6 T6.1).

Outcomes

- Samples collected and forming datasets under the EBP-Nor project are arranged to follow the ERGA and ENA DToL standards in the EBP-Nor database system (<https://databases.ebpnor.org>).
 - Sampling information, provided by EBP-Nor sampling personnel, is guided by attribute constraints through the CBF (or sampling sheet) which enhances consistency and FAIRness of metadata before data submission.
 - Data providers of the EBP-Nor project are recommended to use the EBP-Nor database system and to follow the set standards to achieve FAIR data.
 - Adhering to the data standards, particularly ENA standards, sets the foundation for which EBP-Nor datasets can be accessed through the API service of CBF and be used in submission services to public data repositories.